

INCREDIBLE

Innovation Networks of Cork, Resins and Edibles in the Mediterranean basin

Project no. 774632

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Duration of project: 36 months

Coordination and Support Action

H2020-RUR-10-2016-2017 Thematic Networks compiling knowledge ready for practice

D4.2 Website

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Coordinator

Partners

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www.incredibleforest.net

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Reference

Redondo, C. Adams, S., (2018). INCREDIBLE Website. Deliverable D4.2. H2020 project no.774632 RUR-10-2016-2017 European Commission, 12 pp.

Executive summary

INCREDIBLE project address the gap between existing research and innovation, (between knowledge and practice) on the production, collection, transformation and marketing of Non-Wood Forest Products (NWFP) in the Mediterranean. One of the main tools to communicate and disseminate INCREDIBLE proposals, activities and outcomes is the project website.

Contents

1.- Website

- 1.1. Development and objectives
- 1.2. Website address and general structure
- 1.3. iNets subsites
- 1.4. Galleries
- 1.5. INCREDIBLE Blog

2.- Social Media

1.- Website

1.1. Development and objectives

The Communications Strategy of INCREDIBLE project includes (among other actions) the creation of a website as a central tool for communication and dissemination of the project. The maintenance of the INCREDIBLE web portal is under the responsibility of WP4 and the project coordinator and will be so for at least three years after the project's termination.

The aim of the website is to offer a central platform for the communication and dissemination of the INCREDIBLE project activities and results to the thirteen project partners, stakeholders and general public interested in non-wood forest products (NWFP), and sending the message to wider society that forests, managed sustainably by the inhabitants of rural areas, are a great source of wealth that provides us with cork, resins, aromatic and medicinal plants, and edible products such as wild nuts and berries or mushrooms and truffles. Socio-economic activity in our forests also contributes to wildfire fire prevention.

The website also aims to facilitate the sharing of information and ideas between the five innovation networks (iNets) in the project.

This project has the particularity that each NWFP iNet has its own target audience (own stakeholders, own industries, own markets...), so the website has been conceived with a series of general contents (common to all NWFP) and five 'sub-sites' with the same structure, but specific contents for each NWFP. The development of the web has been carried out in such a way that all the contents included in general sections (news, events, blog post...) are indexed in order to be displayed thematically/sectorially in the corresponding NWFP. In such a way that in the subsites of each iNet appears all the information that INCREDIBLE project generates in relation to that NWFP.

Another important aspect of the project is its internationality. Although English is the language of communication among partners and for global dissemination, after several consultations with the Project Management Team and Community of Practice, it was agreed that in order to reach practitioners/stakeholders different parts of the website (main contents) would be translated into the local languages of the project members (Croatian, Greek, Italian, French, Arabian, Portuguese and Spanish).

The website www.incredibleforest.net has a clear design, adapted to any device, as it has been developed following a responsive design or multi-device design, which allows the presentation of its contents on any type of screen regardless of its size or orientation. The mobile phone has become the main Internet access device. That is why the website is specially adapted to mobile devices, so that any user, regardless of the device used, will have all the information and functionalities of the web.

Website main objectives:

- To disseminate and communicate the INCREDIBLE project events, news, activities and outcomes to project partners, stakeholders and the wider public.
- To host the repository of iNet activities and host the Knowledge sharing platform (T.2.3 of WP2)

Website practical objectives:

- Provide, segmented by NWFP, technical and scientific information on the state of the sector (production, processing, marketing).

- Contribute to the visualization of success stories and green entrepreneurship carried out in relation to the NWFPs.
- Promote awareness of the variety of forest products that contribute to the dynamisation of rural areas.

1.2. Website address and general structure

Web content structure

INCREDIBLE website is available at <http://incredibleforest.net>. The choice of domain includes the term "forest", with the aim of making more easily identifiable the connection with the forest world. The extension of the ".net" domain was also chosen to emphasize the strong networking component of this project.

The website includes info about the following contents (to be subsequently revised according to the update on M24 of the D4.1, Communications Strategy).

- **General project information:** objectives, partners, funding source, expected outcomes
- **iNet sub-sites:** public information about each iNet, dissemination materials, call to action/join the iNet, etc.
- **Project activities, outcomes, results:** newsletter, news, Social Media widgets, multimedia, downloadable dissemination materials.

Home page displays a big slider with images and quotes from some iNets coordinators, and the access to main contents (iNets, 'Join an iNet button, upcoming events, last news and partnership).

The main menu of the website (at the top) distributes the contents as follows:

INCREDIBLE web sitemap							
MAIN MENU							
	The project	iNets	Open Calls	Resources	News	Events	Blog
Submenu	Description	Resins	Research-into-Action	iNets Manual		INCREDIBLE Project Events	
Submenu	Objectives	Aromatic & Medicinal Plants		Private zone		Other NWFP events	
Submenu	Expected results	Cork		Knowledge Platform			
Submenu	Consortium	Wild Mushrooms & Truffles					
Submenu		Wild Nuts & Berries					

Contents:

The Project: Includes a main menu and displays information of the project distributed on the submenus “Description”, “Objectives”, “Expected results” and “Consortium”.

iNets: Describes what is an innovation network (iNet), the core tool INCREDIBLE project to promote knowledge on Non-Wood Forest Products (NWFPs) across the Mediterranean basin, and how these iNets allow to seed, collect, generate and disseminate relevant technological, economic, innovative and research knowledge linked to the main NWFP value chains. Five iNets have been launched, and this menu contains the submenus to each of them and who is its coordinator:

- **Cork.** Coordinated by UNAC
- **Resins.** Coordinated by Cesefor
- **Aromatic & Medicinal Plants.** Coordinated by INRGREF
- **Wild Mushrooms & Truffles.** Coordinated by CTFC
- **Wild Nuts & Berries.** Coordinated by INIA

Open Calls: INCREDIBLE project aims to promote open innovation (as an innovation method in which actors from different organisations participate in the innovation process). This section shows how the project will facilitate open innovation, and will include events related to ‘Open Innovation Challenges’ emerging from iNet process and targeting the open community. This will be launched in carefully selected issues.

Best Research-into-Action summary awards (for researchers and practitioners) is other of the activities to promote open innovation and, in addition, to capture new ideas, to mobilise the broader community and to contribute to a mind-set change in relation to science-practice interaction.

Resources: Website users will have in this menu public deliverables and private deliverables will be available only to project partners. **As internal content, that was intended to be hosted on the web, is**

1.4. Galleries

As part of the iNets subsites has been included a tab with graphical information of the events carried out, with a brief introduction. This is a visual way to show how partners project works, how they share their knowledge and how they also learn (from each other, and from stakeholders that attends the events).

THE PROJECT INETS OPEN CALLS RESOURCES NEWS EVENTS BLOG Search 🔍

Facts & figures Roadmap Events and news Blog Join the iNet Galleries

Your language (Automatic translation performed by third parties)
EN AR HR FR EL IT PT ES

Galleries

Science to Practice event: Advances in mechanization of the use of natural resin
Tardelcuende (Soria, Spain) hosted the first Resins iNet 'Science to Practice' day in October, on the 23rd. The event was organized by the Resins iNet to demonstrate the advances on the mechanisation and organisation of resin use. Throughout the event, the innovation challenges in this field were analysed by public and private research entities, who presented their proposals for innovation, both in the field of extraction and in collection, or logistical control of resin collection operations.

[Twitter](#) [Facebook](#) [LinkedIn](#)

Resins iNet Scoping Seminar
The Resins iNet Scoping Seminar was held in Valladolid, Spain, on 8 and 9 May 2018. Here is a small graphical review of the meeting of both days, in which the iNet took its first steps.

Activar

1.5. Blog

As part of the philosophy of collaborative work, and as another tool for disseminating the science and practice on NWFPs, the website hosts a blog. An editor's account has been provided to the project coordinator and to the coordinator of each iNet.

The main purpose of this kind of content is always generate traffic to the website, through the creation/dissemination of interesting contents apart from the more corporate ones of the project (for this purpose were created the News and Events sections). Engaging the stakeholders is other of the purposes of this kind of contents.

The blog is showed in two ways in the web:

- 1) the whole publications at the main menu called “Blog” (located at the top of the website <https://incredibleforest.net/blog>), and
- 2) the *specific* blog of each iNet, in which only the posts referring to that NWFP are shown (although those referring to ALL will also be shown)

The screenshot displays a web page layout for a blog. On the left, there are two main article cards. The top card features a photo of a person in a green uniform using a chainsaw on a tree trunk. The title is "Bridging the gap in the natural resin extraction sector". The text below discusses advances in mechanization and silviculture techniques. The bottom card features a photo of a forest with the title "NWFP, sustainable bioeconomy and Mediterranean Forestry on the scientific seminar 'Roots to riches'". The text mentions the EFI Mediterranean Facility, EUPFORGEN, and EVOLTREE. To the right of these cards is a sidebar. At the top of the sidebar is a "Subscribe" button and an email input field. Below that is a "News" section with two sub-sections: "Recent" and "Popular". Each sub-section contains a small image and a text snippet for a news item, such as "The Cork iNet Scoping Seminar will be held in Sardinia, Italy on July 11-12, 2018".

Screenshot for example 1)

Your language (Automatic translation performed by third parties)
 EN AR HR FR EL IT PT ES

Blog

Posted by Nuts
 Author: S. Muñoz
The Spanish Operational Group PINEA starts activities with an info day

[in Spanish]

[El Grupo Operativo Pinea "Mejoras e innovación en la producción del piñón nacional"](#)

Tags:
 pine nuts, NWFP, EIP Agri

[Read More](#)

Screenshot for example 2)

About the contents, iNet coordinators can write themselves, or count on collaborations (colleagues, ‘guest-experts’). Initially a determined periodicity was established for the contribution of contents on the part of each iNet coordinator, with total freedom to add post whenever they considered it opportune, outside this system of rotations.

Latest decisions from Project Management Team meetings about posting in INCREDIBLE blog add a new call to iNet coordinators: in order to keep the blog alive, instead of posting by turns, was suggested that each organiser of an event (interregional workshop or science to practice) will have to write a post after each event to explain in less technical words the most important take-home message.

2.- Social media

At the project kick-off meeting, participants agreed that it would be most profitable to use the social networks of all partners, making the project visible through the hashtag #incredibleforest. Existing networks for NWFP will also be explored and utilised where possible.

Subsequent discussions amended this plan to create project social media accounts on Twitter and LinkedIn:

- On Twitter: @Incredibforest

- On LinkedIn: INCREDIBLE Project

In D4.1 and the Starter Kit provided to partners, were noted these **recommendations for use**:

- The project hashtag will be used every time the project is referenced
- URL shorteners can be used to get more characters
- It will be used in partners' Twitter, Facebook, Instagram accounts, etc.
- Accompany the tweet/post whenever possible with an image (increase attention). Other project partners or media can be tagged in the post, thus broadening the audience reach.
- Initial contents will include non-time-specific posts in the networks of each partner with brief information about the project and a link to the INCREDIBLE web.
- Take advantage of events and publicity related to the forestry world, rural development, entrepreneurship, environment, etc.
- Interact and maintain feedback with stakeholders.

Both documents also have some **content suggestions** to feed their actions on social media:

Announcing events, project milestones, outcomes, etc. It will also be useful for promoting project concepts and related ideas. Some initial proposals include:

- 5 products that you did not know came from resin
- The 10 most frequent aromatic plants in Mediterranean forests
- 6 principles for rural development
- 10 simple ways to prepare mushrooms / to eat truffle
- Notable dates related to forestry world such as:
 - World Day of Environmental Education: January 26
 - World Wetlands Day: February 2
 - International Day of Forests: March 21
 - World Water Day: March 22
 - World Meteorological Day: March 23
 - Day of the (Mother) Earth: April 22
 - World Day for Biological Diversity: May 22
 - World Environment Day: June 5
 - Tree Day: June 28
 - Soil Conservation Day: July 7
 - World Habitat Day: October 3
 - International Mountain Day: December 11